

**SPATIAL ANALYSIS OF THE EDUCATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE IN CITY OF
JALANDHAR USING REMOTE SENSING AND GIS**

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ABSTRACT

The paper examines the distribution of educational infrastructure in Jalandhar city, Punjab, India. It also examine the different levels of existing educational institutions in city of Jalandhar. This paper also identify the numerical availability of different levels of schools, colleges and universities as well that comes within the city. In addition to this, the paper also analyze the spatial assessment of educational institutions in the Jalandhar city till year 2020.

The paper also reveals the different categories of schools in Jalandhar city in the State of Punjab at the city level.

In addition to this, the study also shows the different Levels of Schools in the year 2020 in Jalandhar under Municipal Corporation area.

This paper also assess the present status of availability of the educational institutions in Jalandhar city.

KEYWORDS - Educational infrastructure, remote sensing and GIS

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the major social infrastructure. It is a center area for accomplishing the goals of employment, development of human asset and prompting in overall advancement through proficient utilization of assets and resources. Proper education framework develops individual's information, ability, positive attitude, mindfulness and feeling of obligation towards rights and obligations and bestows inward solidarity to confront mistreatment, embarrassment and disparity.

Education, being an immense subject, but the current part has been divided into various levels of Education in Jalandhar city, Punjab. There is a segment on different levels of education from lower to higher education levels.

Education comes under one of the crucial Social infrastructure. Social infrastructure is inevitable to accomplish the target of economic development, quality of life and social turn of events. Openness to social infrastructure is one of the significant indicators of evaluating quality of life in human settlements. In urban planning, the social infrastructure has hierarchical order, for example Network/community, District, and City level amenities. These amenities together incorporate health/wellbeing, education, and socio-cultural, religious as well as recreational exercises. Instruction impacts the nature of labor accessible in the metropolitan territories. Educational facilities influence financial development and advancement which make employment and business openings.

Social Infrastructure is a part of the infrastructure sector. It typically covers the resources that oblige social organizations. As it is mentioned in the table beneath, there are the illustrations of Social

Infrastructure Assets that covers the schools, colleges as well as universities.

Sarwar Jahan and Toshikatsu Oda (2000) have done an examination on the distribution of public facilities in Dhaka, Bangladesh: a spatial analysis. They have used the method spatial analysis and they found out that the some wards and Thanas are considerably more evolved regarding a particular facility. Nonetheless, others are lagging behind the mean level of improvement of the city regarding the facility. Jianquan Cheng et. al. (2004) have done a study on urban growth of china using cellular automata CA. Remote sensing and geographical information systems (GIS have demonstrated to be effective for monitoring urban growth. The discoveries from this exploration recommend that this procedure can be utilized to Interpret and visualize the effective and active process of urban development. H.S. Sudhira et. al. (2004) have done a study on Urban sprawl with the help of GIS, Remote sensing, Urban dynamics, as well as Spatial and temporal analyses. They found out that due to the expanding populace of India as could be, the pressures on land and the assets are likewise expanding. Antonio P'aez et. al. (2004) have done a study on spatial statistics for urban analysis: A review of techniques with examples. They used the techniques like modifiable areal unit issues, Geographic Information Systems, spatial association, spatial heterogeneity, spatial measurements, metropolitan investigation. . They discovered that later on, it appears to be likely that improvement and use of spatial measurable techniques for metropolitan investigation will in general draw all the more intensely on different wellsprings of hypothesis. Jahangeer Afzal Parry et. al (2017) have done a study on locational analysis of ration depots in Jammu and Srinagar urban centers Jammu and Kashmir, India. They have used the technique like GIS. They found out that the status of the existence of the facilities more than that of the city as a overall, however the other thirty two wards which implies the 47% have lack in the arrangement of the formulization of the ration stores.

OBJECTIVE

1. To study the distribution of different levels of educational institutions (Schools, colleges and Universities) in Jalandhar city.
2. To examine the existing multiple levels of educational institutions in the city.
3. To identify the numerical availability of multiple levels of educational institutions in city.
4. To analyze the spatial assessment of educational institutions in Jalandhar city with the utilization of remote sensing and GIS.

DATA SETS

The data related to educational infrastructure like distribution of educational institutions collected from various departments and its location collected using Hand Held GPS of Schools, Colleges and Universities. The information related to educational infrastructure, different departments has been consulted to provide the information. Census report, Master plan report and Map of Jalandhar, Detailed report of Jalandhar has been taken as the secondary data. Satellite imagery, GIS software, Google earth imagery, demographic and administrative maps have been taken to map the distribution of educational infrastructure in urban areas of the Jalandhar city.

PRIMARY DATA SOURCES

1. Georeferencing and digitization of administration boundaries of India, Punjab has been done from published data on Bhuvan.

2. Georeferencing and digitization of Ward boundaries from Municipal Corporation Jalandhar report has been done.
3. Identified GCPs/ Location of Schools, Colleges and Universities and created point layers in ARC GIS Desktop 10.2.1.
4. Digitize/Import the pattern and distribution of educational infrastructure on shape files and created maps.

SECONDARY DATA SOURCES

1. Educational data has been obtained from the following web portal: www.schools.org.in and www.epunjabschool.gov.in to achieve the objectives.

METHODOLOGY

To prepare the base map of Jalandhar city, Georeferencing and digitization of administration boundaries of India, Punjab has been done from published data on Bhuvan.

Georeferenced and digitization of Ward boundaries from Municipal Corporation Jalandhar reports and also identified the GCPs/ Location using the Hand Held GPS of Schools, Colleges and Universities, in order to locate the educational infrastructure facilities.

STUDY AREA

Jalandhar city positioned at 31° 34' 48" N and longitude 75° 34' 48" E with an area of approximately 2632 km² and average elevation of 228 meters above mean sea level (748 ft.). The city is a sports hub and lies close by the Grand Trunk Road and is easily accessible by well-established railway tracks and good roads. The Jalandhar is 144 km northwest of Chandigarh, which is the state capital of Punjab and Haryana and also one of the union territory of India. There are astounding medical centers and amenities in Jalandhar which incorporate treatment centers and hospitals with availability of experts and specialists. The Municipal Corporation of Jalandhar claims that the city has more than 423 medical centers, a case that will make it the city with the most elevated number of medical centers in South Asia. The state Punjab has become very urbanized in character as it is urbanizing quickly and its future is by all accounts metropolitan. With urbanization remaining at 33.95%, Punjab is positioned at fifth major urbanized province of India after Tamil Nadu with 43.86%, Maharashtra with 42.40%, Gujarat with 37.35% and Karnataka with 33.98% and it comes under most urbanized states in the northwest locale of the country. The level of metropolitan populace in Punjab has been on the ascent persistently.

National Highway 44 (old NH1) connects Jalandhar with Srinagar in the northern most part of India and Kanyakumari in the southern end of India (Kashmir to Kanyakumari)-a perpendicular transportation axis. En-route from Srinagar downwards, it connects Jalandhar with Jammu, Pathankot, Ludhiana, Ambala, Karnal and Delhi in the regional context. Through NH-3, Jalandhar is connected with Atari border, Amritsar, Adampur Airport, Hoshiarpur (Punjab), Kullu and Manali of Himachal Pradesh. NH-703 links Jalandhar with Nakodar, Jagraon, Barnala, Mansa and Sardulgarh. NH-703A links Jalandhar with

Kapurthala, Sultanpur Lodhi, Lohian and Makhu. Thus, Jalandhar reflects convergence as well as divergence of road transport which makes it the ideal transport Hub. Similarly, Jalandhar city being located on the main junction of Jammu and Atari railway lines, is linked by this trunk route with major urban agglomerations of India namely; Jammu in the north, Kolkata in the east, Hyderabad, Chennai and Bengaluru in the south, Mumbai in the southwest, Ahmedabad and Jaipur in the west. It is also linked by railways with Nawanshahr, Hoshiarpur, Kapurthala, Firozpur and Sri Ganga nagar in Rajasthan.

Fig 1

Fig 2

In Punjab, Jalandhar city has so many educational institutions. It can be easily said that Jalandhar is providing well educational facilities in northern part of India. This research divides the education further into different levels from lower to higher education.

DIFFERENT LEVELS OF SCHOOLS, COLLEGES AND UNIVERSITIES

This paper reveals education includes different levels of schools and all kind of colleges and universities in Jalandhar city. The different levels of schools that includes the Primary schools, Upper primary schools, Secondary schools and senior secondary schools as well.

Additionally, this paper also includes all kinds of colleges and universities that comes under city. Education is one of the major social infrastructures.

Education infrastructure - It includes Schools, Colleges (all kinds), and Universities (all kinds).

Fig 3

Schools are further divided into different levels –

1. Primary schools
2. Upper primary schools
3. Secondary schools
4. Senior secondary schools

STATUS OF AVAILABILITY OF EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN JALANDHAR CITY

Multiple levels of School Education: Primary, Upper Primary, Secondary and Senior Secondary

The education in Jalandhar city is provided to the students by the different educational and academic institutions. The city is providing education at different levels like primary schools, upper primary schools, secondary schools, senior secondary schools. The prestigious colleges and university in the city of Jalandhar provide higher and advanced education in specialized disciplines.

The education in the city has obtained noteworthy accomplishments through the foundation of different schools, colleges and university in Jalandhar. The students start their education at the young age and primary schools are the most vital phase of education in first five years and establishing the framework for the character, mentalities, social certainty, and habits, learning skills and communicating capabilities of students. Different types of basic skills like speaking, reading, writing and arithmetic are acquired at this stage.

The primary schools form and set up the youthful personalities that set out on the excursion of academics. There are one hundred thirty four primary schools in the Jalandhar city.

Some of the primary schools of Jalandhar city are listed underneath:

1. SS Model school Kailash Nagar
2. Adarsh siksha kendar Panj Peer

3. Cambridge Public school
4. Decent public school Rama Mandi
5. NCLP Special school

The Jalandhar city is providing one hundred nine upper primary schools. Some of the upper primary schools are listed below:

1. Satguru Model School Jaimal nagar
2. Vikas Model school
3. ACE Public school
4. Dev Raj public school
5. Dr Ambedkar school

Secondary and Senior Secondary levels of education are also considered as inevitable part in individual's life. Classes 11th and 12th give the students the choice of joining various courses, including arts, science and commerce to encourage their entrance into the field of work. There are one hundred fourteen secondary schools and one hundred twenty four senior secondary schools in Jalandhar city.

Some of the schools that provides the secondary and the senior secondary school education to the students are listed below:

1. Shivalik Public school Bashir pura
2. Sri Guru Nanak Public Senior Secondary School Preet nagar
3. St. Soldier Divine Public School
4. Apeejay Public school Rama Mandi
5. Doaba Khalsa Model Senior Secondary School

SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF EDUCATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE FACILITIES

Total Number of Schools in Jalandhar City

Fig 4

Total Number of Colleges in Jalandhar City

Fig 5

Total Number of Universities in Jalandhar City

Fig 6

AVAILABILITY OF COLLEGES AND UNIVERSITY OF ALL KINDS IN JALANDHAR CITY

Jalandhar city has also established various colleges and institutes that provide different types of degree level courses in various disciplines of academics. There are also some Technical colleges in the city. Some of the technical colleges are Government Polytechnic College for Women and the Mehar Chand Polytechnic college, Dr. Ambedkar National Institute of Technology, Guru Nanak Computer & technical

college, Kcl Institute management and technology, CT Group of Institutions, Punjab College of Engineering, City institute of technology and research, St. Soldier Management And Technical Institute, St. Soldier Polytechnic College, St. Soldier Institute of Engineering and Technology, Apeejay Institute of Management & Engineering Technical Campus, are the colleges providing technical training to the students. The Dayanand Ayurvedic College, Jalandhar has a medical institute that was established prior to the independence of India. Jalandhar city provides fifty five colleges and one university that is Guru Nanak Dev University, Jalandhar.

The educational facilities in Jalandhar city have accomplished significant achievements.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, it has been noticed that the Jalandhar city has more existing educational facilities. It is therefore correct to say that Jalandhar city is providing well educational infrastructure.

REFERENCES

- Adekunle, Aderamo and Aina (2011): “Spatial Inequalities in Accessibility to Social Amenities in Developing Countries: A Case from Nigeria”. Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences, 5(6):316-322, 2011 ISSN 1991-8178.
- Bhagat R. B (2010), “Access to Basic Amenities in Urban Areas by Size class of Cities and Towns in India”. International Institute for Population Sciences, Mumbai-400088.
- Cheng, J. Masser, I. (2004). Understanding spatial and temporal processes of urban growth: cellular automata modelling. Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design, volume 31, pages 167 - 194.
- Jahangeer Afzal Parry et al.2017, Locational analysis of Ration Depots in Jammu and Srinagar Urban Centers Jammu And Kashmir, India. Int J Recent Sci Res. 8(5), pp. 17047-17053. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.24327/ijrsr.2017.0805.0271>
- Jahan, S. T. O. (2000). Distribution of Public Facilities in Dhaka, Bangladesh: A Spatial Analysis. Bulletin of the Faculty of Human Development, oda@kobe-u.ac.jp
- Sudhira, H.S. Ramachandra, T.V. Jagadish, K. S, (2004). Urban sprawl: metrics, dynamics and modelling using GIS. International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geo information5 (2004) 29–39.
- Scott, A. P. (2004). Spatial statistics for urban analysis: A review of techniques with examples. in Geo Journal. 61: 53–67, 2004. September 2005 DOI: 10.1007/s10708-005-0877-5.
- Salauddin M. (2009), “A spatial analysis on the provision of urban public Services and their deficiencies: A study of some selected blocks in Khulna city”, Bangladesh. Theoretical and Empirical researches in urban management, special number April 2009: Urban issues in Asia.